

The Impact of Automation and AI on Turnover Intention: A Study of Employee in the Workplace

TABLE I. VARIABLES AND INDICATORS

Code	Question	Ref
Artificial intelligence usage		
AIU1	It is interesting to use AI.	[1] [9] [3]
AIU2	AI can help get work done better.	
AIU3	AI is essential for the development of community society.	
AIU4	AI is necessary for everyone.	
AIU5	AI produces more good than bad.	
AIU6	I think AI makes life more convenient.	
AIU7	AI helps me solve problems in real life.	
Loss of skills/expertise		
LSE1	I fear that when using AI, employees may lose their expert status.	[2] [6] [10]]
LSE2	I fear that when using AI, specialized work-related skills will not be needed anymore.	
LSE3	I fear that when using AI, certain specializations can be replaced.	
LSE4	I fear that when using AI, employees may feel less competent.	
AI advantageousness		
AIA1	AI are (will be) faster than human.	[4] [1] [3]
AIA2	AI (will) provide more accurate information than human.	
AIA3	AI are (will be) able to provide information in more languages than human.	
Perceived adaptiveness		
PAD1	I think it would give a good impression if I used with the AI.	[4] [2] [5]
PAD2	I think people will be happy to see me using AI.	
PAD3	I think the AI could adapt to my need.	
AI identity threat		
AIT1	If I use AI, people in my group will not support me.	[2] [5] [8]
AIT2	Using AI makes me feel not respected by others in my group.	
AIT3	Using AI makes me feel not confident that I understand it well enough to get the job done.	
Loss in decision making		
DM1	I believe there is a good match between my decision and AI.	[1] [3] [5]
DM2	I believe AI decisions will fit into my life.	
DM3	I believe AI can help me in my work.	
Human laziness		
HL1	I know what to do but don't want to do it.	[1] [8] [11]]
HL2	I always postponing what should be done.	
HL3	I avoid more complex jobs, affairs or assignments.	
Job insecurity		
J11	Chances are, I will soon lose my job.	[4] [6] [1]]
J12	I am sure I can keep my job.	
J13	I feel insecure about the future of my job.	
J14	I think I might lose my job in the near future.	
Changes of work		
CHW1	The introduction of AI increases my area of responsibility.	[2] [5] [7]]
CHW2	The introduction of AI makes my job more important than before	
CHW3	Since the introduction of AI, I am responsible for more things	
CHW4	By the introduction of AI, I am responsible for more tasks	

CHW5	Since the introduction of AI, my organization expects me to take on more responsibility	
Turnover intention		
TI1	I think a lot about leaving the company	
TI2	I am actively searching for an alternative to this company	[4] [2]
TI3	As soon as it is possible, I will leave this company	[1]